

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Pocketboer II

More performant operation of pocket digesters

Pocketboer 2 aimed to find solutions for persistent problems with pocket digesters. It encouraged the implementation of those solutions at many existing and future plants to improve performance.

Pocket digesters

These small-scale digesters produce biogas from on-farm biomass to meet their energy demand. The electrical power of these installations does not exceed 200 kW. Most installations can currently be found on dairy manure.

Sustainability

Biogas and digestate are produced after digestion. The biogas is valorised to electricity and heat using a combined heat and power unit (CHP), while the digestate can be spread on the field as a high-quality organic fertiliser or soil improver.

GHG emissions are reduced by (partly) avoiding long-term manure storage and by replacing (part of) the fossil fuels required to meet the farm's energy demand.

Three Pillars

- 1) Stimulating knowledge exchange between operators of pocket digesters, partners and other stakeholders (e.g. Facebook group).
- 2) Investigating, addressing or solving persistent technical bottlenecks (e.g. via measurements, cost-benefit analysis,...).
- 3) Administrative guidance (e.g. certificates/investment support,...), individual advice and training.

Results

- 1) Hands-on information to increase awareness of interested farmers.
- 2) Improved digester performance.
- 3) Demonstration of the positive impact of pocket digestion.

Pocket digester

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our journey!

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